

GEOGRAPHICAL SCIENCES

SEASONAL ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS OF THE BULGARIAN DANUBE RIVER AND THEIR RELEVANCE FOR RIVER-BASED TOURISM

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Abstract

River-based tourism is strongly influenced by environmental seasonality, particularly in large rivers such as the Danube. This study examines the seasonal atmospheric and hydrological conditions along the Bulgarian coast of the Danube River using 24 years of mean monthly data. Mean monthly air temperature, air pressure, relative humidity, river water temperature, and river levels from six ports are analyzed alongside ice occurrence statistics from five stations. The analysis focuses on recurring seasonal regimes and their implications for tourism suitability, accessibility, and operational constraints. The results indicate a pronounced seasonal structure governing river usability, with a relatively long period of favorable conditions for tourism activities and a limited winter constraint linked to ice formation. The study provides an environmental baseline for tourism planning.

Keywords: Danube river, river tourism, river navigability, environmental data.

Introduction

Tourism activities in are mostly shaped by environmental variability and seasonal accessibility. Inland waterways such as the Danube support a wide range of tourism products, including river cruises, recreational boating, angling, waterfront cultural tourism, and nature-based activities.

Along the Bulgarian stretch of the Danube, tourism development remains closely tied to navigability, climatic comfort, and the reliability of hydrological conditions (Ivanova P., 2015). Understanding the typical seasonal environmental conditions should be a first prerequisite for assessing tourism viability.

The factors which contribute for the development of cruise tourism on the Danube River are:

1. Resource availability of riverside destinations, namely:

- a wealth of recreational, natural, anthropogenic, and cultural-historical resources;
- opportunities for practicing specialized types of tourism in riverside areas and cities, such as ornithological, ecological, ethnographic, adventure, route-exploration, educational, religious, etc.;
- good transport infrastructure, proximity and easy access to tourist sites in the interior of the country.

2. Favourable navigation conditions on the river throughout all seasons.

3. Established network of passenger terminals in most port cities.

4. Presence of a panoramic view along the river.

Unlike studies focused on climate change detection, this research utilizes mean monthly climatological data aggregated over a 24-year period. While this limits the ability to assess temporal change, it enables a detailed characterization of “normal” seasonal conditions that tourists, operators, and planners are most likely to encounter.

In this article, the author presents an analysis of the navigation conditions in the Bulgarian section of the

Danube as a key prerequisite for the development of cruise tourism in the northern part of the country. A large amount of statistical data has been processed and presented, obtained with the kind assistance of the official state institutions – the Executive Agency “Study and Maintenance of the Danube River” (EAEMDR), which is responsible for maintaining the river's navigability.

The aim of this study is to present the environmental seasonality along the Bulgarian Danube in terms of tourism-environment interactions, focusing on river accessibility and winter constraints related to ice occurrence.

Literature analysis

The Bulgarian part of the river is in the lower reaches, which are characterized by greater width, calmer waters, and more densely populated coastal areas. Unfortunately, however, cruise tourism on the Danube is underdeveloped. Bulgarian tourist ships account for only 1% of all ships on the river. Specialized tourist infrastructure (with the exception of passenger ports) is virtually non-existent in the country, while it is present in all other Danube countries (Vasileva, 2010).

The navigation situation throughout the year and its impact on the development of cruise tourism is an integral part of the overall description of the factors that determine the success of the river tourism. With its 2,414 navigable kilometers (Danube Commission 70, 2019), the Danube provides ample opportunities for both commercial freight transport and tourist transport. The river passes through or along the borders of nine European countries (Dávid & Madudová, 2019), making it particularly interesting for tourist trips.

The characteristics of river navigability and aspects for cruise tourism have been described by a number of Bulgarian and foreign researchers. The literature review on these issues includes publications from the

last twenty years, which shows that interest in the research problem is relatively recent. Kabakchieva and Karcheva present the advantages and disadvantages of river cruise tourism by comparing it to sea cruise tourism (Kabakchieva D., Karcheva T., 2019). Seasonality, frequent shore excursions, and diverse landscapes are some of the characteristics that determine whether conditions are suitable or less suitable for the development of this industry (Mavrova-Guirguinova, 2020), (Ioana-Toroimac & Vîrghileanu, 2025).

River cruise tourism is popular throughout the world. In her study entitled "River Tourism," Vasileva V. reviews the major rivers around the world where various types of tourist services are offered (Vasileva V., 2010). Vasileva identifies the Danube as one of the major rivers in Europe with enormous potential for the development of the industry. The popularity of this tourist product in Europe is also aided by some secondary factors such as the dense population of the continent, a culture of demand for the product, concentration of remarkable sites of cultural, research, cognitive, religious, and other interest (Marinov V. et al., 2014).

Research methodology and analysis

The study draws on:

- Mean monthly air temperature, air pressure, and relative humidity from six ports
- Mean monthly river water temperatures and river levels from the same locations
- Annual statistics on ice formation and complete freezing from five stations

All statistics show multi-year mean monthly values, capturing recurring seasonal patterns rather than interannual variability.

Given the aggregated nature of the dataset, the analysis is explicitly descriptive and relational rather than predictive. The study does not infer trends or future changes but examines:

- Seasonal distributions
- Spatial differences along the Bulgarian Danube
- Environmental conditions relevant to tourism use

This approach aligns with tourism-environment research, where baseline environmental suitability often matters more than long-term climatic change signals.

The study is based on primary and secondary data, which include observation, examination of extensive statistical material, analysis of hydrometeorological information.

To achieve the objectives of the study, the author sought the cooperation of the state authorities Executive Agency "Study and Maintenance of the Danube

River" (EAEMDR) and IAMA. The data and results shown cover different periods over the last thirty years.

Analysis of the results

The Danube River is the only inland waterway in the Republic of Bulgaria. The Bulgarian section is located in its lower course. Navigation on the river is permitted in the deepest water area, which is marked with buoys and is well maintained. The EAEMDR, which is responsible for maintaining the waterway provides information on the navigational situation, meteorological and hydrological information for ships sailing in the Bulgarian section. The following river water level ranges have been adopted to establish the navigation regime (Danube Commission, 2019):

- Low level – below 200 cm;
- Medium level – from 200 to 500 cm;
- High level – above 500 cm.

Navigation conditions are undoubtedly the most important factor that contributes to or hinders the development of cruise tourism on the Danube. Seasonal changes in weather conditions lead to the appearance and existence for a certain period of time of phenomena such as ice drift, freezing of sections of the river, falling water levels, and the appearance of rapids. During some periods of the year when the water level of the river is below the minimum navigable level, sections of difficult navigation are formed. At critically low water levels, navigation is suspended. The Republic of Bulgaria is a party to the 1948 Belgrade Convention and the 1955 agreement between the then People's Republic of Bulgaria and the Romanian People's Republic. Under these agreements, Bulgaria is obliged to maintain and improve the fairway, the part of the river where a safe depth for navigation is ensured.

The navigation conditions on the Danube River change rapidly throughout the different seasons of the year. The strategic objectives of the EAEMDR include activities that help maintain the waterway in a usable condition throughout the year. The agency has the resources to make adjustments to the waterway and install additional navigation marks to ensure the safety of navigation (EAEMDR, 2020). Meteorological conditions are the main factor contributing to specific navigational difficulties for shipping, such as thresholds, changes in the curvature of bends, ice drift, freezing, etc. Twenty five-year statistics for the period from 1994 to 2018 show similar conditions of hydrometeorological elements along the entire length of the Bulgarian section. Data from the meteorological stations "Novo Selo," "Lom," "Oryahovo," "Svishtov," "Ruse," and "Silistra" refer to the following elements:

Fig. 1. Mean monthly temperatures for the period between 1994 and 2018 for the Bulgarian coastline of the Danube.

Source: EAEMDR

Fig. 2. Mean monthly atmospheric pressure for the period between 1994 and 2018 for the Bulgarian coastline of the Danube.

Source: EAEMDR

Fig. 3. Mean monthly air humidity for the period between 1994 and 2018 for the Bulgarian coastline of the Danube.

Source: EAEMDR

Fig. 4. Mean monthly Danube river levels for the period between 1994 and 2018 for the Bulgarian coastline.

Source: EAEMDR

Fig. 5. Mean monthly water temperature levels for the period between 1994 and 2018 for the Bulgarian coastline of the Danube.

Source: EAEMDR

The above-mentioned meteorological elements create conditions for one of the most dangerous situations for navigation on the river – the occurrence of freezing and ice drift.

The Bulgarian section of the Danube provides favorable conditions for navigation even during the winter period. Ice formation is restricted to winter months and affects only part of the year. From a tourism perspective, ice occurrence represents a predictable seasonal constraint rather than a persistent risk. Stations with lower winter water temperatures and lower river levels experience more frequent ice formation, limiting navigation-based tourism during this period. The meteorological factors that cause the water to freeze are air temperature, water temperature, and water level. Figures 1, 4, and 5 show that from December to the end of

March, conditions are potentially suitable for freezing. Fifteen -year statistics from 2007 to 2023, provided by the EAEMDR, show that ice phenomena in the Bulgarian section of the Danube River are becoming increasingly rarer. The confinement of ice to a narrow seasonal window suggests that tourism planning can effectively avoid this constraint. However, with the advent of global warming, the risk of ice phenomena is becoming particularly small, as seen from the ice conditions figures below. The data below describe the state of ice phenomena from the control stations in Novo Selo, Vidin, Svishtov, Ruse, and Silistra. This provides an overview of the entire section of the river from Novo Selo to Silistra (Figs. 6 and 10) and the main ports with a real share in cruise ship services, Vidin, Svishtov, and Ruse (Figs. 7, 8, and 9).

Fig. 6. Ice conditions at Novo Selo, км 833,6

Source: EAEMDR

Fig. 7. Ice conditions at Vidin, км 790,2

Source: EAEMDR

Fig. 8. Ice conditions at Svishtov, км 554,3

Source: EAEMDR

Fig. 9. Ice conditions at Ruse, км 495,6

Source: EAEMDR

Fig. 10. Ice conditions at Silistra, км 375,5

Source: EAEMDR

The above data show that the Danube River offers good navigational conditions, even during the winter season. Ice formation is possible when meteorological and hydrological factors coincide – a prolonged period of sub-zero air temperatures below -5°C and low water levels, i.e. 250 cm and below. Over the last 15-20 years, navigation difficulties have occurred during the periods 2007-2008, 2011-2012, and 2016-2017 for about 25-30 days, when partial freezing of the river was observed. Ice drift is also considered a risk to navigation due to the potential danger of damage to the propulsion and control systems of ships. Statistics show that these phenomena are rare on the Bulgarian section of the Danube, which makes it navigable almost all year round.

Mean monthly air temperatures define a clear gradient throughout the year. The winter months of December, January and February are characterized by low temperatures and low river levels potentially creating suitable ice phenomena conditions, while late spring, summer, and early autumn provide thermally favorable conditions for safe navigation along the Danube.

Relative humidity and air pressure exhibit seasonal variability that influences perceived comfort and weather stability.

Water temperature follows atmospheric seasonality with a damped amplitude. Warmer water temperatures during late spring and summer enhance recreational activities such as boating, fishing, and riverside leisure tourism. Mean monthly river levels indicate seasonal variability that affects navigability and access to river infrastructure. High spring water levels generally support cruise tourism and navigation, while late summer low-water conditions may impose operational limitations on larger vessels.

The results provide an environmental baseline that tourism planners and stakeholders can use to align infrastructure, marketing, and activity scheduling with typical river conditions.

In maintaining navigability, the responsible Bulgarian institutions are also guided by the established European standards for the dimensions of the fairway - a minimum depth of 2.50 m at low water levels, a width

of 180 m, and a curve radius of 1,500 m under all conditions, both during daylight and nighttime hours.

Discussion and conclusions

The information presented so far shows that the factor of "navigation conditions" should not be considered a limiting factor for the development of cruise tourism on the Bulgarian section of the Danube. Over the last years, there has been a noticeable improvement in the infrastructure to and around tourist sites of interest in the country.

The seasonal environmental regime of the Bulgarian Danube supports a relatively long tourism-operational season. Spring and autumn emerge as particularly favorable periods, combining thermal comfort, navigability, and scenic value. Winter tourism remains limited due to ice occurrence and low temperatures, while summer tourism may occasionally be affected locally by low water levels. These findings highlight the importance of seasonally adaptive tourism products rather than uniform year-round development.

This study demonstrates how mean monthly environmental data can be effectively used to assess tourism-relevant river conditions without relying on trend analysis. The Bulgarian Danube exhibits a well-defined seasonal structure, offering extended periods suitable for river-based tourism while maintaining predictable seasonal constraints. This finding is essential for sustainable tourism development, particularly in river corridors with multifunctional economic and environmental roles.

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